

21st CENTURY LEARNING SKILLS, MOTIVATION, AND MATHEMATICAL PROFICIENCY OF COLLEGE STUDENTS: BASIS FOR MATHEMATICAL PROFICIENCY ENHANCEMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the extent of 21st-century learning skills, mathematical motivation, and mathematical proficiency among second-year college students at Ema Emits College Philippines. Additionally, the study examines the relationship between the said variables. The research employed a quantitative approach, collecting data from 120 second-year college students at Ema Emits College Philippines across various courses who had already taken the subject Mathematics and the Modern World. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to arrive at the correct interpretation of data. Findings revealed that students exhibited a high extent of 21st-century learning skills, particularly in collaboration, critical thinking, and communication, but a low extent in creativity. However, students demonstrated a low extent of motivation in terms of nature of mathematics, problems, and solutions, suggesting a need for intervention. Furthermore, students have varying mathematical proficiency levels. Results revealed that each dimension of 21st-century learning skills is significantly and positively correlated with all indicators of mathematical proficiency. Similarly, 21st-century learning skills are statistically significant to all aspects of mathematical motivation. Likewise, mathematical motivation is significantly correlated with all domains of mathematical proficiency. This highlights the importance of developing 21st-century learning skills and mathematical motivation in students to improve their mathematical proficiency.

Keywords: *21st Century Learning Skills, Mathematical Motivation, Mathematical Proficiency, Collaboration, and Nature of Mathematics*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics studies patterns, relationships, logic, creativity, applications, and many other things. This nature is key to educating people to be mathematically adept and to be aware of the power of grounding mathematics in the lives of people and society. Educators can foster a deeper appreciation of this vital discipline by bridging gaps in motivation and understanding through effective educational practices. Moreover, it is among the most complex topics in the curriculum. Researchers have effectively pinpointed the various factors that significantly influenced pupils' achievement over the past few decades, particularly in mathematics (Layar et al., 2024), such as problem-solving approach (Albay, 2020), cognitive and affective aspects of learning (Cipriano, 2020).

Despite efforts conducted by educators to make the discipline enjoyable and engaging. Still, surveys and studies consistently reveal that mathematics is widely perceived as a challenging subject in education, often resulting in low performance among students. Cuemath survey found that 89% of parents believe mathematics is the most challenging subject for their children, with 77% expressing concerns about the quality of math instruction in schools (New Indian Express, 2018). This result must be prosecuted seriously, and different countries have different avenues. Thus, many dire situations remain to be addressed despite numerous attempts to promote mathematical proficiency for learners globally. These include strategies to improve mathematical progress across different learners and a crystallized strategy for educators. Strategies, motivation, and 21st-century skills take a crucial part in the development of learning, particularly in mathematics.

The PISA 2022 results highlight the essential requirement for education reforms to focus on content knowledge, student engagement, and curiosity to enhance learning outcomes. The Philippines ranked third-lowest in science and sixth-lowest in mathematics and reading among 81 countries assessed. This reflects a modest gain compared to previous evaluations, with the Philippines finishing at the bottom of the list for reading and second to last for mathematics and science in the 2018 PISA cycle. Still, in general terms, the results indicate serious challenges, with fewer than one in four Filipino students reaching at least the minimum proficiency levels for all subjects tested. However, developing a love of learning, which doesn't necessarily correlate with performance in Mathematics, is paramount to solutions for countries struggling in this area.

On the National Achievement Test (NAT), the outcome was extremely low, especially in the discipline of mathematics, where it scored 28.7%, the lowest of all subjects for the academic year 2014–2015. Given that it fell short of the passing standard specified by the National Educational Testing and Research Center, this demonstrated

that pupils genuinely do not acquire a mastery level of comprehension in mathematics (NETRC). This result implies that there is a need to recalibrate student competence.

In the school context, the average performance or the mean percentage scores of SHS students in their Mathematics subjects transitioning to college in EMA EMITS College Philippines is approximately 34.67%. This means that there is a problem concerning mathematical proficiency among learners. This problem should be addressed by determining direct factors influencing mathematical proficiency. Two of these are the manifestation of 21st-century skills and the mathematical motivation of learners.

Concerns about mathematical proficiency have grown increasingly urgent as students around the globe struggle to meet expected competency levels. It is vital in developing cognitive skills and is a core competency in a society that is increasingly knowledge-based, with a high premium on analytical and problem-solving skills. However, despite its importance, numerous studies demonstrate ongoing issues of decline or stagnation in student mathematical achievement, calling the efficacy of existing practices into question (OECD, 2021).

Several studies have examined the impact of traditional teaching methods on students' mathematical proficiency, and there have also been various innovations in teaching in recent years. Still, overall results are poor mainly because math, for most students, is discouraging and challenging to learn. To illustrate, Sunzuma and Maharaj (2019) suggested greater integration of group learning practices in ways that can enhance learning outcomes. It was found that the traditional method of explaining math to students (rote memorization) did almost nothing to enhance math competence and motivation for students learning mathematics. So, it is essential to address these issues and prepare students with the tools and abilities they need to succeed in an increasingly complex world. The need to fill this knowledge gap is why the researcher conducted this study. Generally, the study determined the 21st-century learning skills, motivation, and their correlation to the mathematical proficiency of 2nd-year college students at EMA EMITS College Philippines.

At the core of 21st-century learning skills are communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking. Several studies show that 21st-century learning skills are contributing factors to improved mathematical proficiency. The study of Corpuz (2024) reveals a positive correlation between students' 21st-century learning skills and their mathematics performance. Correspondingly, research has demonstrated that effective mathematical communication proves to be a vital element in improving performance in mathematics and reducing anxiety in mathematics. Students better understood mathematical concepts, improving problem-solving skills and overall performance (Lomibao et al., 2016). Moreover, integrating collaborative learning strategies within mathematics instruction improves academic performance and increases student motivation (Abendan et al., 2024). In addition, implementing creativity-focused strategies in mathematics education leads students to make considerable improvements in problem-solving skills and overall achievement in mathematics (Tongola et al., 2024). Furthermore, Duru and Chinedu (2023) state that students with strong critical thinking

skills tend to perform better in mathematics as they can analyze problems logically, evaluate multiple solution strategies, and apply mathematical concepts effectively.

Motivation is another contributing factor to improved math, which is the key to success. Motivation drives performance and interacts with mathematical cognitive strategies. Wild and Neef (2023) found that highly motivated students, whether driven by intrinsic interest or extrinsic goals, tend to adopt more effective learning strategies, such as problem-solving heuristics, metacognitive regulation, and conceptual understanding techniques. In a critical and advanced learning area like mathematics, students must be motivated to pursue what they started (Broda et al., 2023). Students with strong motivation and self-efficacy tend to persist in their studies, graduate on time, and perform better in their future careers (Wang et al., 2020). Teachers should first change the misconceptions of the learners about the subject. Research indicates that motivated students are more likely to engage deeply with mathematical concepts and persist through challenges. Motivation has been identified as a factor influencing students' mathematics learning. However, the motivation of many people who want to learn is low, possibly due to past negative experiences or the material they study that is not in line with the world. This understanding of the motivational dynamics will support the creation of appropriate teaching methods that captivate students' interests and goals.

Why must motivation practices be recalibrated among learners and their 21st-century skills? This is because the foundation of mathematical learning lies behind the walls of these two. According to Deloviar (2019), there are many gaps concerning this. These two are the common factors that dictate mathematics proficiency. These arguments served as the springboard for the researchers to conduct the study. These arguments strengthen the need for a mathematics enhancement plan to mitigate these pressing circumstances.

In this research, second-year college students are the participants, who have generally taken up the subject "Mathematics in the Modern World," where they learn mathematical ideas and applications for real-life uses that are consistent with current education objectives. As they have an excellent academic grounding in the subject and are familiar with how mathematics relates to everyday life and broader social issues, research into critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills suggests they are well-placed to pursue studies in this area. The balancing act of being sinfully full of skills and knowledge, whilst being open to being skillful and knowledgeable, creates value, insight, and impact in the form of governance, advice, progress reports, empirical evidence, or system-level analysis applied toward 21st-century skills and academic performance boundaries. Studying these experiences and backgrounds can provide insights into how 21st-century learning skills and motivation impact mathematical proficiency. This would serve as a base reference for formulating the mathematical proficiency enhancement plan. Creating an enhancement plan could mitigate underlying circumstances concerning the mathematics learning of college students.

Research Questions

Generally, the study determined the 21st-century learning skills, motivation, and mathematical proficiency of second-year college students at EMA EMITS College Philippines. The findings of this study would serve as a base reference for formulating an enhancement plan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. To what extent do the second-year college students of EMA EMITS College Philippines manifest 21st Century Learning Skills in terms of:
 - 1.1. critical thinking;
 - 1.2. creativity;
 - 1.3. collaboration; and
 - 1.4. communication?
2. To what extent do the second-year college students of EMA EMITS College Philippines manifest Mathematical Motivation in terms of:
 - 2.1. nature of mathematics;
 - 2.2. problems;
 - 2.3. solution; and
 - 2.4. real-life conceptions?
3. What is the level of Mathematical proficiency of second-year college students of EMA EMITS College Philippines in terms of:
 - 3.1. conceptual understanding;
 - 3.2. procedural fluency;
 - 3.3. strategic competence;
 - 3.4. adaptive reasoning; and
 - 3.5. productive disposition?
4. Is there any significant relationship between the extent to which 21st-century learning skills manifest and the mathematical proficiency of second-year college students at EMA EMITS College Philippines?
5. Is there any significant relationship between the extent of manifestation of 21st-century learning skills and the mathematical motivation of second-year college students at EMA EMITS College Philippines?
6. Is there any significant relationship between the extent of manifestation of mathematical motivation and the mathematical proficiency of second-year college students at EMA EMITS College Philippines?
7. Based on the study's findings, what mathematical enhancement plan can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This research employed descriptive-correlational statistics to examine the relationship between 21st-century learning skills, motivation, and mathematical proficiency. The study's descriptive analysis captured the current levels of students 21st

21st-century learning skills, motivation, and mathematical proficiency. Meanwhile, the correlational aspects explored how 21st-century learning skills and motivation correlate with mathematical proficiency.

The study's participants were the second-year college students of EMA EMITS College Philippines who had taken the course “Mathematics in the Modern World” for the school year 2023-2024. The number of participants for this study is determined using G-power, an application tool used to calculate an adequate sample size for correlation-based analysis.

To gather all the information needed, the researcher utilized a researcher-made questionnaire and a test designed to capture distinct but complementary data. The questionnaire measures participants' extent of 21st-century learning skills and motivation, which allows for collecting subjective data that reflects participants' experiences or opinions. On the other hand, the test objectively assesses participants' level of adaptive reasoning, conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, and productive disposition in Mathematics. Primarily, the test consists of ten (10) items, each taken from the Mathematics in the Modern World subject only.

To ensure the reliability of the instruments measuring 21st-century learning skills and motivation, the test-retest method was utilized. Twenty (20) students not included in the study will be asked to answer the questionnaire twice over ten days. By examining the correlation using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation between the scores from the first and second administrations, the stability and consistency of the measurements over time can be evaluated. Additionally, the study used Cronbach's Alpha, another reliability test, a statistical measure that evaluates the internal consistency of a set of items within the instrument. Analysts frequently use Cronbach's alpha to determine and test the reliability of newly constructed research tools. This helps them assess the quality of the tool during the design phase before its actual administration.

In addition, for the context of mathematical proficiency, item analysis was applied to evaluate the quality of test items, focusing specifically on the index of discrimination and the difficulty index. The difficulty index measures the proportion of test-takers who answer items correctly. On the other hand, the index of discrimination was used to evaluate how well an item differentiates between high- and low-performing students. Analyzing them both will ensure that the tests are appropriately challenging and effectively differentiate between varying levels of mathematical proficiency.

To ensure the validity of the research instrument used in this study, construct validity was employed to assess whether the tools accurately measure the intended constructs: 21st-century learning skills, motivation, and mathematical proficiency. To achieve this, the instrument underwent expert validation by professionals with strong academic and practical backgrounds in mathematics education. The panel included a Master Teacher II with a Doctor of Philosophy in Mathematics, an Associate Professor III with a Master's degree in Mathematics, and two Master Teacher I, both holding Master's degree in the same field. These experts reviewed the instrument for content clarity, ease

of use, and relevance to the constructs being assessed. Their feedback was carefully considered and integrated, leading to the finalization of a validated and reliable research tool.

This study used descriptive and inferential statistics to arrive at the correct interpretation of the data. Descriptive statistics organize, analyze, and present data meaningfully, while inferential statistics correlate data and make hypotheses and predictions. For descriptive statistics, the study used the mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage to determine the extent to which the students manifest 21st-century learning skills and mathematical motivation, as well as to assess their level of mathematical proficiency. Meanwhile, inferential statistics used regression to determine the interplay between 21st-century learning skills, mathematical motivation, and mathematical proficiency.

The scope of the study involves analyzing the constructs of how 21st-century skills, such as critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication, prepare students to participate in mathematical concepts and solve problems. Another independent variable that needs to be studied is the mathematical motivation, with indicators such as the nature of mathematics, problem, solution, and real-life conceptions. The dependent variable in the study is mathematical proficiency, which includes conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning, and a productive disposition. Mathematical proficiency is directly about Statistics and Data, one of the competencies of Mathematics in the Modern World subject.

While integrating 21st-century learning skills, motivation, and mathematical proficiency in educational research offers valuable insights, limitations arise when considering their interconnected dynamics. Firstly, 21st-century skills, as an independent variable, cover an array of engaging abilities like critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication, which can be variously defined and not uniformly measured, making research results inconsistent. Additionally, motivation is also an independent variable that is not easy to measure, as it is driven by inextricable intrinsic and extrinsic factors that cannot be delineated or quantified easily. Furthermore, mathematical proficiency as a dependent variable often relies on standardized assessments that may not fully reflect the real-world application of skills or account for variations in cultural and educational contexts.

The study was delimited to the 4Cs of 21st-century learning skills. This study did not cover 21st-century skills such as problem-solving, perseverance, information literacy, technology and digital literacy, media literacy, global awareness, self-direction, social skills, literacy skills, civic literacy, social responsibility, innovation skills, and thinking skills. Additionally, motivation is defined within the context of the nature of mathematics, problems, solutions, and real-life conceptions, not considering broader social, emotional, and other factors that influence students' learning experience. Furthermore, mathematical proficiency is measured using researcher-made tests, which may not fully encompass the diverse ways in which students demonstrate mathematical understanding. Moreover, the

study solely focused on specific competencies of Mathematics in the Modern World. Other mathematics subjects were not included in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Extent of 21st Century Learning Skills

21st Century Learning Skills in terms of:	Overall Mean	SD	Interpretation
Critical Thinking	2.50	0.71	High Extent
Creativity	2.32	0.72	Low Extent
Collaboration	2.73	0.77	High Extent
Communication	2.50	0.76	High Extent

Table 1 shows that the respondents generally demonstrate a high extent of critical thinking, as indicated by the overall mean of 2.50. This is in line with the overall standard deviation of 0.71, indicating a wide variability in respondents' perceptions. This shows that respondents' perceptions are not extremely consistent, meaning some students can employ strong critical thinking while others seem to falter. Findings imply that students possess strong analytical, evaluative, and reasoning skills in solving mathematical problems. Although some students feel proficient in certain aspects of critical thinking, others may struggle to identify assumptions, engage in logical reasoning, question concepts, and detect errors in the analysis. In this regard, educators need effective interventions to strengthen these less adept areas of the students, such as instructional strategies that focus on making assumptions, logical reasoning, and error minimization. These areas can be strengthened to enhance students' critical thinking, especially in solving math problems. This is parallel to the study of Kaur and Kaur (2020), which states that effective teaching methods improve students' reasoning skills and metacognition, leading to better logical reasoning skills when approaching problems. These strategies, when incorporated into the curriculum, make it easier for students to consider problems and arrive at informed decisions. Likewise, mathematical reasoning is more than solving problems; students must generate questions, analyze, and reason to reach correct and well-justified conclusions (Sachdeva & Eggen, 2021).

Moreover, creativity with an overall mean of 2.32 interpreted as a *low extent* suggests that the said respondents seldom or lack confidence in applying creativity in their mathematics learning experience. Furthermore, the illustrated overall standard deviation of 0.72 supports this finding, indicating that the use of creativity in mathematics is not consistently emphasized among respondents. The findings imply that creativity in mathematics is not being fully maximized. There is a need to integrate more creative opportunities into the math classes. Educators should encourage strategies such as visual learning, open-ended problem solving, and real-life math projects. These approaches can encourage respondents to experiment or even design their own mathematical tasks, which will empower respondents for them to be able to see that mathematics is not only a logical or routine procedural subject but also a subject that

fosters imagination and innovation. Mann (2021) shared that fostering creativity in mathematics helps students build connections between concepts, making their knowledge more flexible and transferable across various mathematical domains. Similarly, Amegbanu and Mpuangnan (2023) state that a curriculum that emphasizes the presentation of uniform content rather than developing creative thought excludes an avenue for innovation. In addition, traditional ways of curriculum tend to be convergent, allowing for few responses, which leads to being a creativity killer (Goos & Kaya, 2020).

Furthermore, data revealed that overall, the respondents perceive themselves as actively engaging in collaborative practices during mathematics classes, as presented by the overall mean of 2.73, described as a high extent. The overall standard deviation score of 0.77 indicates a moderate level of variation, meaning, while most students generally agree that collaboration happens to a high extent, some respondents have different or less consistent experiences, as in not all benefit or participate in it equally. Findings imply that the respondents experienced a positive learning environment where collaborative learning, such as group activities, peer discussions, and teamwork, is encouraged. They appear to recognize the importance of social interactions in developing their mathematical understanding. However, it is important to acknowledge that although collaboration is generally practiced, not all respondents engage in the same way. Some may still require additional support or confidence-building activities to fully participate and benefit from collaborative learning experiences. In line with this, Selwyn (2019) argues that students need to have a sense of norms that govern their actions to collaborate well with others. Collaborative learning activities in mathematics, in which students exchange ideas, create opportunities for students to help each other, and enrich their knowledge through interaction and collaborative problem-solving (Abd Algani, 2021; Gamit et al., 2017). Further, collaboration facilitates communication, exchange of strategies, and cooperation in problem-solving and promotes active participation whereby every learner has a different perspective to work toward a common understanding or solution (Smith et al., 2020).

Likewise, communication with an overall mean of 2.50, described as a *high* extent, suggests that respondents recognize the importance of communication in communicative practices such as explaining ideas, listening actively, and valuing feedback. The overall standard deviation of 0.76 suggests that some respondents may still feel hesitant or unprepared to communicate mathematical ideas effectively, despite the positive perception. Findings imply that there is a positive engagement and awareness of communication; however, because of the marginal result, there is a need to help respondents become more confident and effective in expressing their mathematical thinking. This involves putting more focus on developing their ability to explain ideas clearly, use the appropriate mathematical language, and communicate their reasoning with clarity. Through these efforts, respondents are more likely to develop a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts and engage more actively in classroom discussions and activities. This is supported by the findings of the study of Limjap (2021), stating that communication allows students to learn from their peers, providing opportunities for discussions of strategies and the perspectives of others to enhance mathematical understanding and performance. Correspondingly, as Diago and Dielo

(2022) say, when students feel confident in expressing their mathematical thoughts, they are more prone to attempt more challenging problems without the need for external input.

Table 2. Extent of Mathematical Motivation

Mathematical Motivation in terms of:	Overall Mean	SD	Interpretation
Nature of Mathematics	2.49	0.81	Low Extent
Problems	2.49	0.82	Low Extent
Solutions	2.47	0.80	Low Extent
Real-life conceptions	2.52	0.82	High Extent

As shown in table 2, the overall mean for the extent of mathematical motivation is 2.49, indicating a low extent of motivation in terms of nature of mathematics. In line with the overall standard deviation of 0.81, showing some variability in response, signifying that while some respondents are highly motivated, others appear indifferent and disengaged. This suggests that students may not be highly engaged or driven by the different aspects of mathematics, such as problem-solving potential or its interconnections with other disciplines. Findings imply that while some students acknowledge certain aspects of mathematics that could serve as motivating factors, such as its usefulness and problem-solving capabilities, their overall motivation is not strongly driven by those qualities. Likewise, respondents need external incentives such as grades or career relevance to remain engaged. This points to an opportunity for teachers to incorporate more interactive, relatable, and engaging approaches to teaching mathematics, aiming to foster greater intrinsic motivation. This is supported by the claims of Luitel (2019), stating that by understanding the nature of mathematics, the learners could develop flexible thinking and flexible problem-solving that is very much applicable in relevant situations. This foundational knowledge allows students to increase their confidence and skills in mathematics, setting up the stage for success academically and professionally.

Likewise, problems, similar to the previous indicator, the same overall mean and description were observed, suggesting that, as a group, the respondents do not demonstrate strong motivational tendencies when it comes to engaging in mathematical problems. However, the overall standard deviation of 0.82 indicates a moderate variation in responses reflecting diverse attitudes and experiences among the respondents, perhaps influenced by confidence, past performance, or learning environment. Findings imply that while some respondents experience positive emotions when they successfully solve math problems, this sense of motivation does not consistently translate into a proactive or confident approach to problem solving. Some respondents may struggle with self-doubt or hesitation, which could be hindering their overall motivation in terms of mathematical problems. These results point to a need for instructional strategies that build respondents' self-efficacy, such as a gradual increase in problem difficulty, encouraging productive struggles, and celebrating effort as well as success. Parallel to the study of Jaudinez (2019), supporting students to engage with a variety of mathematical problems

encourages students to apply different strategies and develop perseverance and a deeper understanding of mathematical ideas. Furthermore, by problem-solving, students realize that they can use mathematics in everyday life, which leads to a positive perception of the discipline (Sinaga & Situmeang, 2023).

In addition, students generally demonstrate a weak motivation in seeking mathematical solutions, with a computed overall mean of 2.47, described as a *low* extent. The overall standard deviation of 0.80 shows some variations in response, indicating that many students have the same feeling about finding solutions, while some have differing experiences. Findings imply that while many respondents appreciate the benefit and emotional satisfaction that come with arriving at correct mathematical solutions, majority of them believed that they lack confidence, which affects their persistence and willingness to engage deeply in problem-solving tasks. There is a need to reframe mathematical problem-solving as not just a task of getting the correct answer to being embraced as a meaningful, exploratory, and rewarding journey of learning and discovery. This is supported by the study of Velez and Abuzo (2024) that when students have high levels of mathematics self-efficacy and motivation, their problem-solving skills are still very low. These findings imply that educators need to scaffold learning experiences in which students can solve, select, and create problems to be solved by themselves, whereby, in addition, a growth mindset will be fostered. Moreover, Mance-Avila and Guzon (2020) stressed that expressing and refining solutions allow students to rationalize their thoughts, which is essential for pursuing further studies and in the workplace. Additionally, finding an insurmountable solution to complex problems is a key strength of students' confidence and resilience in a great mathematical learning experience (Mainali, 2021).

However, students exhibit a high preference for seeing the value of mathematics in real-life contexts, with a computed overall mean of 2.52, described as a *high* extent. The overall standard deviation is 0.82, indicating moderate variability, implying that students have different perceptions of how they esteem mathematics depending on their experience. Findings imply that students recognize that they need to understand mathematical concepts to meet career goals, that they will use them in the future, and that they are empowered to work on real problems. But some areas show a lack of confidence and practical engagement, allowing for progress. With these, educators must use real-world applications in teaching math to make it more practical and relevant, making students develop a stronger motivation and confidence in using math beyond the classroom. This aligns with the study of Baidoo and Ali (2023), where mathematics is seen as a sort of understanding that relies on relating more abstract mathematical ideas to everyday experiences, which has been documented to improve how learners solve problems and interact with mathematics.

Table 3. Level of Mathematical Proficiency

Mathematical Proficiency in terms of:	Mean	Interpretation
Conceptual Understanding	6.02	Moderate Proficient
Procedural Fluency	6.88	Proficient
Strategic Thinking	4.34	Basic Proficiency

Adaptive Reasoning	4.72	Moderate Proficient
Productive Disposition	4.76	Moderate Proficient

The table shows that conceptual understanding, with a mean score of 6.02 described as moderately proficient, indicating that, on average, respondents possess a fair level of conceptual understanding in mathematics, though with considerable room for improvement. This points to a need for targeted instructional support because enhancing conceptual understanding is critical not only for academic success but also for developing respondents' confidence and long-term engagement with mathematics. This confirms with the study of Andamon and Tan (2018), stating that a strong conceptual understanding helps students link abstract mathematical concepts to concrete applications in their lives, improving problem-solving ability and attitudes toward mathematics. Similarly, in a research study conducted by Wees (2018), students with a strong conceptual understanding of instructional content hold on to and apply what they learn from their instruction.

Meanwhile, procedural fluency, as fostered in the table, in general, respondents fall within the Proficient category for procedural fluency, with a mean score of 6.88. The results indicate that respondents from Ema Emits College Philippines have a solid foundation in procedural fluency, but there is a need for targeted interventions to elevate students' skills, particularly those in the lower proficiency categories. Strengthening both the procedural aspects of mathematics will not only improve overall competence but also foster greater confidence and achievement in future coursework. Educators should prioritize strategies to reinforce procedural fluency, offer tailored support for students with lower proficiency, and challenge those at higher levels to continue developing their skills. This is supported by the study of Inayah et al (2020), that building procedural fluency leads to improved problem-solving ability and understanding of mathematical procedures, thus providing a foundation for success in both academic and real-world contexts, and being able to explain why the order of operations matters prevents students from making some common errors when simplifying expressions. Additionally, as Andal and Andrade (2022) described, procedural fluency is necessary to allow students to appropriately engage with open-ended mathematical tasks. Furthermore, Patiño Jr (2023) asserts that strong procedural fluency allows students to handle accurate algebraic computations better and use their algebraic reasoning skills with confidence and flexibility.

On the other hand, students in general show a limited capacity for strategic thinking and frequently use procedures in routine ways rather than introducing meaningful analytical processes to the problems faced, with a mean score of 4.34 that falls under basic proficiency. The result indicates space for enhancement in the students' strategic thinking facet. Teachers need to focus more on dissecting a problem and looking at it from different angles, and planning divergent paths to a solution. Educators must help students to realize that they can use different strategies, such as working backward, making good guesses based on their current knowledge, and breaking down the problems into smaller parts. Similar to the claims of Abdullah and Fadil (2019), explaining that when students learn and implement HOTS, they then properly go from understanding a problem to planning and carrying out a solution. These highlight the significance of

strategic thinking in mathematical education, which promotes academic achievement and readies students to address problems in the real world through developing analytic skills and decision-making processes (Abdullah & Fadil, 2019; Darma et al., 2018).

Moreover, while most students have basic proficiency, in general, students exhibit a moderately proficient level in adaptive reasoning, as reflected in the mean score of 4.72. The finding suggested that while students have some foundational skills to provide explanations and justifications for their reasoning, they may not apply this ability consistently. This needs an intervention that supports students in sharpening their adaptive reasoning. Educators should strive to construct environments in which students can describe their thought processes for solving problems to help develop skills in critical thinking. And by building a classroom culture that promotes questioning and reflection, students can practice their reasoning and apply it to new contexts. Leveraging metacognitive strategies in conjunction with best practices in adaptive reasoning can put students in the driver's seat of their learning journey. This reasoning is essential to rationalizing math problems to have a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts, logical inferences, and to approach the complex challenges in systematic approaches (Darwani et al., 2020). This is supported by the claim of Stanford (2022), which asserts that adaptive reasoning is a key element to gaining a deep understanding of mathematics. This reasoning process plays an important role in the justification and relation of mathematical problems to ensure a better understanding of mathematical concepts, make logical inferences, and solve complex challenges in a structured way (Darwani et al., 2020). It empowers students to think logically, argue their points, and assess solutions well.

Furthermore, with an average score of 4.76, the students have a moderate level of proficiency in productive disposition. The results show that students perceive that mathematics is important, but they become less confident and unmotivated as the task becomes difficult. Thus, student needs to be supported to build a positive attitude regarding the importance of mathematics. With these, teachers should go ahead and encourage a positive attitude towards learning by focusing on the relevance and utility of mathematics in real life. Also, by promoting a growth mindset where errors are viewed not as failures, but as learning opportunities that allow students to develop confidence and build self-esteem. In addition, integrating real-world applications and teamwork makes learning more fun, relevant, and meaningful. This is parallel to the findings of Chua (2021), stating that in producing adaptive disposition within students, a positive attitude is formed to create a path for learning new concepts and problems in subject areas involving mathematics. Moreover, according to Haji et al (2019), the application of the Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) approach integrated with an outdoor learning approach could be applied to improve students' productive disposition of mathematics. Having a strong and positive disposition toward mathematics will promote students to engage in mathematics with perseverance, which will eventually lead to better learning (Saharani & Abadi, 2024; Haji et al., 2019; Chua, 2021).

Table 4. Relationship between 21st Century Learning Skills and Mathematical Proficiency

21 st Century Learning Skills	Mathematical Proficiency														
	Conceptual Understanding			Procedural Fluency			Strategic Thinking			Adaptive Reasoning			Productive Disposition		
	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P
CT	0.69	0.47	p<.001	0.55	0.30	p<.001	0.53	0.28	p<.001	0.62	0.38	p<.001	0.68	0.46	p<.001
CR	0.63	0.40	p<.001	0.63	0.40	p<.001	0.59	0.35	p<.001	0.62	0.38	p<.001	0.75	0.56	p<.001
CL	0.65	0.42	p<.001	0.59	0.35	p<.001	0.46	0.21	p<.001	0.64	0.41	p<.001	0.75	0.56	p<.001
CM	0.65	0.42	p<.001	0.59	0.35	p<.001	0.53	0.28	p<.001	0.67	0.45	p<.001	0.75	0.56	p<.001

p < .05

The table shows the correlation analysis between the extent of 21st-century learning skills and the level of mathematical proficiency. Data revealed that critical thinking (CT) has a significant positive correlation to mathematical proficiency. As evident, critical thinking has the highest correlation with conceptual understanding [r(120)= 0.69, p<0.001], suggesting that respondents who excel in critical thinking tend to have a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. Strong relationship is also seen with adaptive reasoning [r(120)=0.62, p<0.001], and productive disposition [r(120)=0.68, p<0.001], suggesting that students with good critical thinking skills can connect past knowledge to new mathematical problems and can develop a positive attitude towards mathematics. Meanwhile, a moderate correlation to procedural fluency [r(120)=0.55, p<0.001], and strategic thinking [r(120)=0.53, p<0.001], suggesting that students can recognize the most efficient methods to solve problems and support flexible problem-solving approaches. This is parallel to the claims of Duru and Chinedu (2023), stating that students perform better in mathematics when their critical thinking ability is high because they can logically analyze problems, evaluate multiple strategies to solve problems, and apply mathematical concepts.

Creativity also has a significant positive correlation with mathematical proficiency, with a high correlation especially with productive disposition [r(120)=0.75, p<0.001] and procedural fluency [r(120)=0.63,p<0.001], suggesting that creative learners are not only better at solving problems but also tend to have a more positive mathematical mindset. This is supported by the study of Tongola et al (2024), stating that students with better mathematical creativity develop innovative and flexible strategies to solve mathematical problems, contributing to improving their mathematical abilities. Instead of rote memorization, creative math encourages students to find multiple answers, identify patterns, and transfer ideas to new situations.

Aside from critical thinking and creativity, data show that collaboration (CL) also has a significant positive correlation to mathematical proficiency, with the strongest association to productive disposition [r(120)=0.75, p<0.001]. It is followed by conceptual understanding [r(120)=0.65, p<0.001] then adaptive reasoning [r(120)=0.64, p<0.001]. Interestingly, strategic thinking has a slightly lower but still significant correlation [r(120)=0.46, p<0.001], implying that collaboration plays a stronger role in shaping beliefs and understanding than in planning strategies. This aligns with the findings of Abendan

et al (2024) experiment, as they found that students who engaged in trial tasks through structured collaborative learning settings tend to understand mathematical concepts better than those who study individually.

Furthermore, communication, aside from the other aspects of 21st-century learning skills, is also significantly correlated to mathematical proficiency. Communication, like collaboration, exhibits the strongest correlations with productive disposition [$r(120)=0.75$, $p<0.001$] and adaptive reasoning [$r(120)=0.67$, $p<0.001$]. A moderate correlation procedural fluency [$r(120)=0.59$, $p<0.001$], and strategic thinking [$r(120)=0.53$, $p<0.001$]. The results underscore the role of communication in building confidence, reasoning, and clarity in mathematical thought. This is parallel to the study of Lomibao et al (2016), as they mentioned that as students communicate mathematics in a clear and organized manner, they become aware of mathematical ideas and relationships, and this seems to create a more favorable disposition for success in problem-solving.

Overall, 21st-century learning skills are significantly correlated to mathematical proficiency since all relationships are significant at $p<0.05$, meaning there is less than a 0.5% probability that these relationships are due to chance. This shows that 21st-century learning skills, particularly critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication, play a crucial role in fostering mathematical proficiency among respondents. In a similar vein, Corpuz (2024) found a positive relationship between students' 21st-century competencies and mathematics achievement. The study also indicates that students who have 21st-century learning skills tend to do better in mathematics, as 21st-century learning skills develop better cognitive flexibility, resourcefulness, and wise usage of technology for learning.

Table 5. Relationship between 21st Century Learning Skills and Mathematical Motivation

21 st Century Learning Skills	Mathematical Motivation											
	Nature of Mathematics			of Problem			Solution			Real-life Conception		
	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P
CT	0.70	0.49	$p<.001$	0.73	0.53	$p<.001$	0.71	0.50	$p<.001$	0.62	0.38	$p<.001$
CR	0.73	0.53	$p<.001$	0.73	0.53	$p<.001$	0.68	0.46	$p<.001$	0.67	0.45	$p<.001$
CL	0.60	0.40	$p<.001$	0.64	0.41	$p<.001$	0.57	0.32	$p<.001$	0.63	0.40	$p<.001$
CM	0.77	0.59	$p<.001$	0.78	0.61	$p<.001$	0.73	0.53	$p<.001$	0.72	0.52	$p<.001$

$p < .05$

The table highlights the correlation coefficients (r), coefficients of determination (R²), and significant values (p) between the extent of 21st-century learning skills and the extent of mathematical motivation. Data revealed that there are significant relationships across all variables. This suggests that there are strong and consistent connections between all the 21st-century learning skills measured and different aspects of respondents' motivation in mathematics.

Addressing each point individually, communication shows the strongest relationships across all domains. The computed p-value of less than 0.05 means the null hypothesis is rejected, meaning a significant relationship exists between communication and mathematical motivation. This is proven by the following results: nature of mathematics [$r(120)=0.77$, $p<0.001$], problem [$r(120)=0.78$, $p<0.001$], solution [$r(120)=0.73$, $p<0.001$], and real-life conception [$r(120)=0.72$, $p<0.001$]. This implies that respondents with strong communication skills are more engaged and motivated in understanding mathematical ideas, solving problems, and connecting math to real-life contexts. This is supported by the study of Blašková et al (2016), stating that communication is very important to bring motivation into harmony, which ultimately leads to a better performance.

Next, creativity also shows very strong correlations. This is evident in the computed p-value of lower than 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means there is a significant relationship between creativity and mathematical motivation. In fact, nature of mathematics and problem shares the same significant value of [$r(120)=0.73$, $p<0.001$]. This is followed by solution [$r(120)=0.68$, $p<0.001$] and real-life conception [$r(120)=0.67$, $p<0.001$]. These results highlight that respondents who can generate original ideas and think outside the box tend to be more motivated in approaching mathematics, especially when relating mathematics to practical applications. Parallel to the study of Miranda and Morais (2019), which shows a significant correlation between creative personality and motivation for work. Motivation tends to increase as students consider themselves more creative.

In terms of critical thinking, it can be observed that it is also strongly correlated with mathematical motivation since the r values range from 0.62 to 0.73. Likewise, the computed p-value is below 0.05, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis, meaning a significant relationship exists between critical thinking and mathematical motivation. This verifies that respondents who can analyze, evaluate, and reason logically are more likely to be motivated in mathematics, particularly in problem-solving and situation-related aspects. This is supported by the conclusion of Qardaku (2021) that as students' critical thinking increases, their learning motivation also increases.

Lastly, while the correlation values [$r(120) = 0.57$ to 0.64] for collaboration were slightly lower than the others, still, there is a significant relationship found. Since the computed p-value does not exceed 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, meaning there is a significant relationship between collaboration and mathematical motivation. This implies working with others, through shared problem solving or group tasks, supports respondents' motivation and engagement in mathematics. Similar to the findings of the study of Durksen et al (2017), wherein they identified a significant positive relationship between collaboration and motivational constructs. Research demonstrates that motivation and engagement are higher within collaborative learning environments. Moreover, collaborative learning positively and significantly affected students' academic motivation (Loes, 2022).

Overall, the result implies that critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and

communication enhance mathematical motivation. These skills also show students that math is not a series of abstract concepts to memorize, but a dynamic field that is part of the problem-solving process of life that can bring about real change. Learners are more likely to be motivated, confident, and engaged in mathematical learning if we nurture 21st-century learning abilities. Similar to the findings of the study of Thanyaphongphat et al (2023), the motivation to learn is positively influenced by the integration of 21st-century skills through contextual inquiry project-based learning, or CI-PBL.

Table 6. Relationship between Mathematical Motivation and Mathematical Proficiency

Math. Motivation	Mathematical Proficiency														
	Conceptual Understanding			Procedural Fluency			Strategic Thinking			Adaptive Reasoning			Productive Disposition		
	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P	r	R ²	P
NM	0.58	0.34	p<.001	0.60	0.36	p<.001	0.53	0.28	p<.001	0.54	0.29	p<.001	0.62	0.38	p<.001
PR	0.60	0.36	p<.001	0.62	0.38	p<.001	0.53	0.28	p<.001	0.53	0.28	p<.001	0.63	0.40	p<.001
SL	0.57	0.32	p<.001	0.62	0.38	p<.001	0.52	0.27	p<.001	0.50	0.25	p<.001	0.58	0.33	p<.001
RC	0.52	0.27	p<.001	0.59	0.35	p<.001	0.52	0.27	p<.001	0.53	0.28	p<.001	0.59	0.35	p<.001

p < .05

The table outlines the correlation analysis between the extent of mathematical motivation and the level of mathematical proficiency. Data revealed that mathematical motivation has a significant positive correlation to mathematical proficiency.

Looking at the individual relationship, data shows that problems has the highest correlation to mathematical proficiency in all aspects, especially with productive disposition [r(120)=0.63, p<0.001], procedural fluency [r(120)=0.62, p<0.001], and conceptual understanding [r(120)=0.60, p<0.001]. These suggest that students who are motivated by mathematical problems develop a deeper understanding of the mathematical concepts, reinforce mathematical procedures, and build confidence and resilience to overcome challenging problems. This is supported by the study of Jaudinez (2019), which states that having students wrestle with various mathematical problems prompts them to try a range of strategies and provides an environment for nurturing resilience and richer concepts of mathematics. Moreover, problem-solving helps students recognize the relevance of mathematics in real-life situations, thereby leading to a favorable view of mathematics (Sinaga & Situmeang, 2023).

Next from problem with the highest correlation to mathematical proficiency is observed in nature of mathematics. With the highest correlation to productive disposition [r(120)=0.82, p<0.001], and procedural fluency [r(120)=0.60, p<0.001], suggesting that students who are motivated in the nature of mathematics see math as a system of consistent procedures that can be applied flexibly. This is supported by the study of Watson et al (2021), which states that the nature of mathematics is an essential element of mathematical proficiency as it increases students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills creatively. Understanding the nature of mathematics also underpins flexible and adaptive thinking and problem-solving to assist the use of mathematics in relevant

contexts (Luitel, 2019).

Then, solution with a high correlation to procedural fluency [$r(120)=0.62$, $p<0.001$], suggesting that students reinforce step-by-step accuracy in solving math problems. While moderately correlated to most of the domains of mathematical proficiency as to conceptual understanding [$r(120)=0.57$, $p<0.001$], strategic thinking [$r(120)=0.52$, $p<0.001$], adaptive reasoning [$r(120)=0.50$, $p<0.001$], and productive disposition [$r(120)=0.58$, $p<0.001$]. This is supported by the study of Mance-Avila and Guzon (2020), which stressed that expressing and refining solutions allow students to rationalize their thoughts, which is essential for pursuing further studies and in the workplace.

Lastly, while the correlation values [$r(120)=0.52$ to 0.59] for real-life conception are not as high as the other, still a significant positive correlation was found. This shows that students who see the relevance and application of mathematics in daily life make abstract concepts easier to understand, develop flexible problem-solving that strengthens fluency, and enhance their reasoning and ability to solve math problems. This is supported by the study of Baido and Ali (2023), which states that focusing on the relationship between more abstract mathematical ideas and everyday experiences enhances the ability of learners to solve problems and engage in mathematics.

Overall, the result indicates that if the students are motivated, they will perform better in mathematics. In line with the research of Wild and Neef (2023), students with high motivation, regardless of whether the motivation stems from an interest in the subject matter or from extrinsically driven motives, are more likely to engage in effective learning strategies such as problem-solving heuristics, metacognitive regulation, and conceptual understanding. And what matters for students is that those with high intrinsic and extrinsic motivation to learn mathematics have better performance by being more engaged, persistent, and confident in problem-solving (Zhang et al., 2021).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the Second-year college students at Ema Emits College Philippines excel in analytical and interpersonal skills; however, there is a need to focus on enhancing their creative thinking abilities. At the same time, second-year college students at Ema Emits College Philippines tend to focus more on real-life applications of mathematics rather than the subject's abstract or theoretical aspects. Moreover, the second-year college students at Ema Emits College Philippines demonstrate varying levels of mathematical proficiency, with procedural fluency emerging as their strongest aspect. Additionally, strengthening 21st-century learning skills such as critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity positively influences and improves learners' mathematical proficiency. Fostering 21st-century learning skills such as critical thinking, communication, collaboration, and creativity effectively boosts learners' motivation to learn and engage with mathematics. In conclusion, increasing student motivation positively enhances their proficiency in the subject.

Recommendations

Based on the drawn conclusions, Ema Emits College Philippines should incorporate activities and opportunities that promote innovative problem-solving, interdisciplinary projects, and collaborative exercises that aim to help not only the second-year learners but the entire student body cultivate their creative abilities alongside their existing strong analytical and interpersonal skills. At the same time, Ema Emits College Philippines must integrate a balanced curriculum or, if possible, introduce interactive learning activities such as group discussions, debates, or case studies and the like that emphasize both real-life applications and the foundational theoretical concepts, encouraging learners to see the value of abstract mathematical principles in solving practical problems. Additionally, Ema Emits College Philippines must implement targeted interventions and instructional strategies such as workshops, tutoring sessions, or additional resources that focus on strengthening conceptual understanding, strategic thinking, and adaptive reasoning, complementing their strong procedural fluency. Moreover, Ema Emits College Philippines could incorporate activities, training sessions, and workshops that encourage students to collaborate and communicate while tackling mathematical challenges, thereby further enhancing their 21st-century skills and improving their overall mathematical proficiency.

Schools and educators should secure an interactive and dynamic classroom environment and discussions that promote interactive learning experiences, encouraging teamwork, stimulating innovative problem-solving approaches, and using technology to support deeper understanding. Likewise, to inspire greater learning and confidence, schools and educators should continue on delivering engaging lessons with clear, achievable goals, celebrate learners' progress, and foster a positive and supportive classroom atmosphere that encourages continuous growth. Furthermore, future researchers can utilize other variables that can potentially correlate with mathematical proficiency, like cognitive skills, study habits, affective factors, etc.

Mathematical Proficiency Enhancement Plan

I. Introduction

LAMP stands for **Learning, Application and Mathematical Proficiency**, this model is a comprehensive, interconnected educational approach taken to advance students' math learning. It starts with **the Learning** phase, which helps students build a strong foundation of math skills and knowledge and nurtures essential 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, collaboration and communication. Next is the **Application** phase, where the key focus is on the ideas that are used to solve certain problems in the real world, thus encouraging learners to be involved in a process of problem-solving, examining practical situations, and becoming aware of the usefulness of math in everyday life (motivation). The **Mathematical** component grounds the process in logical reasoning, procedural fluency, and conceptual understanding, ensuring students build strong cognitive connections. Ultimately, the goal is to achieve **Proficiency**—a balanced development across five key dimensions: conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning, and a productive disposition toward math. Students through the LAMP framework learn mathematics, use it, think mathematically, apply knowledge meaningfully and bring utility leading to deeper engagement and immersions for long term success.

II. Rationale

Guided by the results of the study, the proposed plan was designed. Students should have a more profound understanding of math concepts, they should be able to apply them in other contexts, and lastly, they can tackle and solve very challenging problems. In addressing this need, **LAMP—Learning, Application, Mathematical Proficiency**—framework was formulated giving a logical and at the same time a very pliable approach to the formation of the whole human beings of the mathematicians.

The LAMP framework is of the opinion that students cannot reach true mathematical proficiency by only following isolated instruction but by the meaningful linkage of learning, application, and reasoning.

III. Mission

To develop full **Mathematical Proficiency**, as defined by five interrelated strands: conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence, adaptive reasoning, and productive disposition.

IV. Core Components, Strategies, and Assessments

Core Components	Strategies and Activities	Assessment
Critical Thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Analyzing real-world problems and proposing solutions• Logic, puzzles and deductive games• Socratic questioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Rubrics that assess reasoning, logic, and evidence used➤ Oral recitation➤ Performance task

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case-based learning • Error analysis in mathematical contexts 	
Creativity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual learning • Open-ended problem solving • Real-life math projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Portfolios ➤ Creativity rubrics evaluating originality ➤ Product output
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group activities (e.g., collaborative poster, concept map) • Cooperative learning structures (e.g., Jigsaw, Think-Pair-Share) • Peer discussion • Team challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Use of a rubric to evaluate group activities ➤ Peer evaluation ➤ Short individual quiz ➤ Reflection logs ➤ Short group presentation
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explicit teaching of speaking and listening skills • Oral presentations • Debates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Rubrics and listening checklist ➤ Peer and self-assessment forms ➤ Feedback forms
Nature of mathematics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore unsolved mathematical problems • Create math timelines showing how they develop • Watch and discuss videos on mathematical insights • Sharing insights about the evolution of mathematical ideas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reflection journals ➤ Concept maps of interconnected ideas ➤ Essay or video blogs
Mathematical Problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly math challenges or puzzle corner (math relay, brain teaser stations) • Problem-solving workshops (open-ended problem) • Competitions or math games 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Self or peer evaluation ➤ Portfolios ➤ Problem-solving rubrics ➤ Reflection sheet
Mathematical Solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage multiple solutions, representation and strategies • Compare and contrast varying solutions • Use of manipulatives and digital tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reflection journal ➤ Comparison chart ➤ Observation checklist ➤ Short oral or written presentation
Real-life Conception	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate real-world data and problems into the lesson • Apply math to student interest • Design surveys and analyze results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Real-world problem solving ➤ Presentations related to real-life contexts

Conceptual Understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use visual representations (e.g., diagrams, models, number lines) to explore math ideas. • Implement inquiry-based learning, encouraging students to discover patterns and connections. • Conduct concept-mapping activities to show links between topics. • Integrate real-life contexts to help students see the meaning behind abstract ideas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Concept-based quizzes ➤ Performance tasks with explanation components ➤ Reflective journals
Procedural Fluency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide structured, step-by-step practice. • Regular practice with routine and non-routine problems. • Spaced repetition and formative quizzes. • Use math drills and timed activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Timed problem-solving exercises ➤ Diagnostic tests on algorithms and steps ➤ Error analysis tasks
Strategic Thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teach problem-solving heuristics (e.g., guess and check, work backward, draw a diagram). • Present non-routine problems and encourage multiple solution paths. • Encourage strategy with math games 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reasoned Strategy Tasks ➤ Problem-solving journals ➤ Problem solving with group discussions, analyzing solution paths
Adaptive Reasoning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask Socratic questions that push the thinking behind the reasoning. • Engaging peer teaching and criticism of solutions. • Use math debates or discussions. • Encourage a culture of questioning and reflection. • Conduct “Think Aloud” sessions where students verbalize their reasoning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Rationales and justifications written out ➤ Oral reasoning in presentations
Productive Disposition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply growth mindset strategies (e.g., praise effort, not only outcomes). • Cultivate a growth mindset about mathematics. • Use interesting real-world applications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Reflections for students and goal-setting sheets ➤ Resilience and participation in solving challenges

V. Implementation Timeline

Time Frame	Focus
Month I	Diagnostic assessments, mindset building, and skill mapping
Month II	Strategy execution, collaborative learning, and motivation enhancement
Month III-IV	Mastery checks, real-life project-based tasks, personalized challenges
Month V	Summative evaluation, reflections, student-led conferences

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Also, study highlights the used of ethical considerations to protect the concerned individual and prevent misuse of information. Participants received thorough study materials and are free to leave without consequences. The researcher also ensures that private data stays hidden to avoid unwanted access. Participants' responses are collected and maintained so that it would be nearly impossible to tie answers to individual people. Ethical permission is also sought from the relevant ethics committee to ensure that the study follows the ethical norms and principles. These processes maintain the survey's integrity and reduce potential harm. Considering these ethical concerns, the study safeguards the participants and improves the validity and reliability of the findings.

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